

1 Samuel 2:1-10

also known as “Hannah's Prayer”

Data source: Prayer in the Ancient World

By Taylor Gray, Penn State

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

Entry tags: Religious Group, Israelite Religion, Canaanite, Poetry, Judeans and Israelites, Levantine Religion, Semitic, Ancient Western Asia, Prayer, Text, Northwest Semitic, Afro-Asiatic, Central Semitic, Judaism, West Semitic, Language, Hebrewic, Ancient Hebrew, Ammonite

1 Samuel 2:1-10 is an ancient Hebrew poem contained in the opening narrative of the Samuel-Saul-David narrative cycle in 1-2 Samuel. In 1 Samuel 1, Hannah, a wife of Elkanah the Ephraimite, beseeches Yahweh for a child because she is barren, and Elkanah's second wife Peninnah “provokes” (*ka'as) Hannah on this account. In desperation, Hannah prays to Yahweh, asks for a child, and vows to dedicate the boy to Yahweh if he grants her request. Yahweh hears Hannah's vow, and she conceives a child, the prophet Samuel. Hannah then dedicates Samuel to Yahweh in Shiloh. 1 Samuel 2:1-10 presents the character's celebration of her god and the narrator explicitly states that “Hannah prayed” (wattitpallēl ḥannâ) the material in 1 Samuel 2:1-10. Based on manuscript and internal evidence, 1 Samuel 2:1-10 was added to the narrative after initial composition, which explains its superficial connection to the preceding narrative. 1 Samuel 2:1-10 is composed in classical Hebrew verse that is intertextually coordinated with other biblical poetry, such as Deuteronomy 32:1-43 and 2 Samuel 22≈Psalm 18 (among others). The poetic lines are written in typical Northwest Semitic two-part (bicola) and three-part (tricola) parallelism. The poem extols Yahweh as the prototypical god, a god of knowledge and wisdom, one who exacts justice and mercy, grants childbirth, controls life, death, and the whole earth. Finally, the poem celebrates Yahweh's victory over the enemies of his faithful (ḥasîd) and assures that Yahweh gives strength to his (unnamed) king. If the poem of 1 Samuel 2:1-10 circulated independently before being added to 1 Samuel, it could have functioned as a royal victory song during or shortly after the monarchic period (ninth to fifth centuries BCE). In its current context, the poem functions as a literary prayer for the character Hannah that follows the miraculous birth of Samuel.

Date Range: 900 BCE - 500 BCE

Region: Ancient Israel and Judah

Region tags: Israel, Judah, Palestine, Levant

Ancient Israel and Judah

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Auld, Graeme A. I & II Samuel: A Commentary. Old Testament Library. Louisville: Westminster John Knox Press, 2011.

- Source 2: McCarter, Kyle P. 1 Samuel: A New Translation with Introduction, Notes, and Commentary. The Anchor Bible 8. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press, 1980.
- Source 3: Gray, Taylor. "Hannah's Prayer (1 Sam 2:1-10)." In *Prayer in the Ancient World*, edited by Daniel K. Falk and Rodney A. Werline. Leiden/Boston: Brill, forthcoming.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://brill.com/display/serial/PAMW?language=en>
Notes: Gray, Taylor. "Hannah's Prayer (1 Sam 2:1-10)." In *Prayer in the Ancient World*, edited by Daniel K. Falk and Rodney A. Werline. Leiden/Boston: Brill, forthcoming.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.stepbible.org/?q=version=THOT|reference=1Sam.2&options=LNVUHG>
- Source 1 Description: STEP Bible provides an online, interactive version of the Masoretic Text, the most complete and commonly used witness of the Hebrew Bible.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.academic-bible.com/en/bible/BHS/1SA.2>
- Source 2 Description: Academic-bible.com provides an edition of Biblia Hebraica Stuttgartensia (Masoretic Text) along with English and German translations of the Hebrew Bible.
- Source 3 URL: https://www.sefaria.org/l_Samuel.2?lang=bi
- Source 3 Description: Sefaria provides multiple resources for reading primary biblical texts in Hebrew and English. It also provides access to a wealth of Jewish commentary literature (among literatures).

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Written

Inked

- with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Papyrus

Notes: It is uncertain what the earliest biblical texts were written on. Earliest manuscripts of 1 Samuel from the Qumran are papyrus. Ancient Hebrew, unlike cuneiform languages like Akkadian, was not pressed into clay. Most ancient Hebrew literature has likely perished.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Unknown

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Unknown. In later Jewish scribal circles, there is a complex set of rituals involved in the construction, preparation, and transmission of sacred texts.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Field doesn't know

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Field doesn't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is worth noting that in the storyworld of the Hebrew Bible, the tablets that Moses receives on Sinai are stored in the ark of the covenant (which functions as a sort of aniconic representation of Yahweh).

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Text does not make specific reference, but we can imagine that the royal administration in both Israel and Judah sponsored scribal groups. Some were probably responsible for the texts that later became "biblical."

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– I don't know

Notes: 1 Sam 2:1-10 was received as scripture. When it was composed was it considered "scripture"? Unlikely in the modern sense of the word.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is debate about the archaic nature of the poem. Some see it as a dialectical or literary artifice. Others see it as genuinely representative of an older stage of the Hebrew language. There is not a strong concentration of archaisms, unlike Exod 15, Judg 5, or Deut 32, though. The poem does make use of some uncommon lexemes (‘lš, ‘tq, e.g).

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– Yes

Notes: The language used is distinctly poetic and employs (some) rarer lexemes. There are cases of style-switching in the Hebrew Bible. That is, the intentional effort to manipulate the language to read/sound dialectical or "foreign" (e.g., Rendsburg 2019)

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– Yes

Notes: That biblical Hebrew, specifically biblical poetry reflects the spoken language of Iron Age Israel is unlikely. Biblical Hebrew is curated and stylized literary language.

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals?

– Yes

Notes: In antiquity, the composition of texts like 1 Sam 2:1-10 were done by elite scribes who were trained in literary arts. The same is true today for those who copy and transmit the Hebrew Bible in Jewish traditions.

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Other [specify]: Unknown. Early on the texts are composed in Hebrew without thought. However, there is a sense that Hebrew takes on an authoritative status in early Judaism (e.g., the prologue to Ben Sirah). In rabbinic tradition and beyond, Hebrew is the "sacred tongue" (lšwn hqdš).

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– No

Notes: There is no strong delineation between religious and non-religious institutions in the ancient world. The political administration sponsored things like cult and scribal groups.

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– Yes

Notes: The text in question can be studied by anyone in any language. There is no limitation.

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Eventually in Second Temple Judaism, yes, oral tradition did support these texts. How far back these traditions go remains a matter of debate.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Text does not specify.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that this text circulated independently as a victory psalm used in celebration after a victorious battle.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Multiple versions of Hannah's Song, and 1 Samuel exist. These include (among others) the Masoretic Text, texts from Qumran (notably 4QSam^a). For a more thorough textual history of 1-2 Samuel see Ulrich 2020.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: In antiquity, it is clear that various versions of the same biblical text were tolerated, authoritative, and venerated. 1-2 Samuel is an excellent example of the fluid nature of biblical literature before the rabbinic period. So is Jeremiah. The same could be said regarding translations of the text. Ultimately, what is at stake is the question of what is "proper."

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

Notes: Currently, some of the oldest witnesses to 1-2 Samuel (though incomplete) are not the same as the Masoretic Text (See Ulrich 2020). The antiquity of the text does not necessarily make them more authoritative, however.

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

Notes: There are differences among the witnesses of 1-2 Samuel. Which readings are "best" are established on the grounds of text critical methodologies (for overview, Tov 2011; Brotzman and Tully 2016).

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Yes

↳ Among debates about proper versions of the text, how is authority established?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– No

Notes: The oldest extant versions of 1 Samuel are among the Dead Sea Scrolls. One of which features as a comparative text for Auld 2011 (see bibliography). Also, Greek translations of 1 Samuel are known from late antiquity (e.g., Codex Vaticanus) Most contemporary Bibles and scholars prefer the Masoretic Text, but there are readings from 4QSam^a and the Old Greek that are preferred at times. The critical apparatus in BHS is a useful starting point.

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

↳ How is the authority established?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Why scrolls were included in the Jewish "canon" is unknown.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– I don't know

Notes: The biblical canon varies depending on religious and denominational boundaries (Schmid and Schröter 2021; Barton 2019). Religious authorities will explain that the canon is immutable, but the notion of a scriptural canon is a relatively late idea in both Judaism and Christianity, at least in relation to the composition of the "canonical" literature.

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– Yes

↳ How are the volumes ordered?

–Specify: The Jewish "canon" is composed of three categories: Law, Prophets, Writings. Genesis through 2 Kings is ordered according to a narrative structure. The prophets are ordered for less clear reasons. Though subcollections exist, such as the Twelve ("minor prophets"). The same is true of the Writings. The Psalms, according to some, have a distinct order/structure, as does Proverbs. Other books in the Writings are grouped together on the basis of catch words/themes.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: Not in text

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The belief articulated is subtle. There is an allusion to the netherworld (Sheol) in v. 6 and the text suggests that Yahweh is able to both kill and bring back to life. One should not read too far into this expression, but it does suggest a view of afterlife. On death in the Hebrew Bible, see Suriano 2018).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

Notes: In the Hebrew Bible, the realm of the afterlife is Sheol (referenced v. 6).

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Notes: There is no serious debate among scholars. Sheol is the realm of the dead/afterlife in the Bible. Common idea among ancient Southwest Asia communities.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: Yahweh is praised as the prototypical god in v.2, similar phrases express Yahweh's superiority in other texts like Ex 15:11; 2 Sam 22:32; Isa 44:8 (to list only a few). On the implications of this phrase see Singletary 2021.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

Notes: While Yahweh is generally anthropomorphic, this text does not ascribe anthropomorphic imagery to him explicitly.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Notes: The text states that the "Most High will thunder in heaven" which is an explicit reference to Yahweh's status as a sky god, perhaps better, a Levantine storm god.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– Yes

Notes: To an extent. The king is referenced at the very end of the prayer and receives strength from Yahweh. For more explicit associations with the king and divinity, see Psalm 45.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

Notes: Not in this text, but consider 2 Samuel 7, Psalm 2, or Psalm 89.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– Yes

Notes: Benevolence towards his "pious."

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– No

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: Bears the epithet "Rock." Common conceptualization in ancient Southwest Asia.

Notes: This title and related lexemes are quite common in ancient Southwest Asian religious thinking. Deities are regularly equated with rocks, stones, cliffs, and mountains. On the use of this epithet see Knowles 1989; Gray 2023.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Text calls Yahweh "God of knowledge." His knowledge is specifically related to knowledge of human action, which he adjudicates.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– I don't know

Notes: Text does not specify.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Notes: While implicit, Yahweh's control of life and death, along with the earth (as mentioned in the poem) suggests that his knowledge is far-reaching/without limit.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: See comment above.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– I don't know

Notes: See comment above.

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Notes: Presumably, based on v.3b.

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Notes: See comment above.

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– No

Notes: Only actions are mentioned. States of mind/intentions are not addressed.

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– No

Notes: Text does not mention.

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

Notes: Not specified.

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– I don't know

Notes: The question is unclear. The extent of Yahweh's knowledge in this text is not systematically outlined. The implication based on the text's assertion that he is the supreme deity, and a god of knowledge, would suggest there is little he does not know. However, this is an interpretation rather than an explicit statement in the text.

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: Yahweh is explicitly the subject of verbal action in v.6ff.

↳ Can reward

– Yes

↳ Can punish

– Yes

- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
 - Notes: This is implied in vv.4-5, where Yahweh is not the subject of action, but the implication is that Yahweh is responsible for the described state of affairs.
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - Yes
 - Notes: It is clear that Yahweh's attitude towards the wicked results in being "cut off." This certainly can be understood as a negative emotion.
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
 - Notes: Not in the text.
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - No
 - Notes: The text positions Yahweh as the prototypical god. The only one worthy of praise.
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
 - Specify: Child birth provision
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - No
 - Notes: Not in this text specifically. Yahweh does interact with the human characters in the preceding chapter, and throughout the Hebrew Bible.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Notes: There is nothing in the text that would suggest this.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: The rhetorical question posed in v.2 explicitly mentions other deities ("there is no holy one like Yahweh," "there is no Rock like our god"). The point is that Yahweh is superior to them, but the text implies that there are other divine beings and they are capable of influencing the world, but Yahweh is supreme.

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

Notes: The text does not describe seeing Yahweh, or any other divine being. Though, characters like Moses, Isaiah, Micaiah, Ezekiel, Daniel, and others view the divine body. On the divine body in the Hebrew Bible see Sommer 2009; Stavrakopoulou 2021.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

Notes: Not in this text. Moses is an example of someone who is (maybe) touched by Yahweh (Ex 33:17-23).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– No

Notes: Yahweh, see comments above.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: Not in this text. In other cases, Yahweh's messengers and members of his divine council act in the world. Examples include cherubim (Gen 3; Ezek 10), seraphim (Isa 6), "the destroyer" (Exod 12), the accuser (Job 1-2), Michael (Daniel 10, 12), etc.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– I don't know

Notes: Unspecified in the text.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
– I don't know
Notes: Not in the text.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
– I don't know
Notes: Not in the text.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
– I don't know
Notes: Not in the text.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
– Specify: There is nothing outlined about the other divine beings in the text.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Notes: Based on other biblical evidence, the reference to other divine beings in v.2 would suggest the presence of a pantheon (e.g. Deut 32; Pss 82, 89:6, 8 [ET vv.5, 7] [e.g.]; Job 1-2; 5:1; 15:15). It is important to note, that it is unclear what the organization of the pantheon is in 1 Sam 2:1-10.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?
– I don't know
Notes: The organization isn't specified. On Levantine panthea structures, see Smith 2000.

↳ Organized hierarchically?
– Yes
Notes: Based on the rhetoric of v.2, Yahweh is the supreme deity. On Yahweh's ascent to the top of the pantheon in Israel see Parker 1995 and response in Machinist 2011, also Edelman 1996.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?
– Yes
Notes: Ostensibly, Yahweh's dominance is specific to his power and superiority. Not to mention the fact that "pillars of the earth" (lit. "pourings of the earth") belong to Yahweh (v.8).

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: The text does not say.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: None.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: Though, the epithet "Rock" is used in amulets (Barkay 2004) and later Jewish magical texts (Aramaic incantation bowls, e.g.).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: In the text, Yahweh seems to reverse the typical structures of life. The powerful are brought low, the poor are exalted, the barren bear children, the satisfied sell themselves for food, etc. This is typical of Yahweh's many biblical texts. He is a god who disrupts and reverses power dynamics.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

Notes: In so far as the text implicitly advocates for righteousness, loyalty to Yahweh, and piety (vv.9-10).

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– No

Notes: Not mentioned. Though other Yahweh worshippers are killed in the Hebrew Bible, albeit for problematic ritual practice (e.g., Exodus 32).

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– No

Notes: Yahweh kills his enemies in the text.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– No

Notes: Not in this text.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

Notes: Though this is the case elsewhere in the Hebrew Bible. For instance, Leviticus 18.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– No

Notes: Not in this text.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

Notes: This is the narrative context outlined in 1 Samuel 1. Hannah fulfills her vow by dedicating Samuel to the Shiloh sanctuary. Admittedly, the poem in 1 Sam 2:1-10 does not explicitly engage with oath-keeping.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– No

Notes: Unmentioned, though a theme in Proverbs.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– No

Notes: Not in this text specifically. The Hebrew Bible has a complex relationship with issues of "sorcery" and "magic." A multitude of texts prohibit such activities. Nevertheless, it does appear at times (at to be efficacious) (e.g., Exod 7-12; Num 5; 1 Sam 28).

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
 - Specify: Unspecified.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text describes both a current state of affairs in which (apparent) punishment is described (vv.4-5), but also anticipates punishment (vv.9-10).

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Notes: Yahweh.

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Notes: Punishment is/will be visited upon the proud, arrogant, and wicked.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– No

Notes: Not necessarily. It is done out of justice for the oppressed and the righteous.

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that it inspires piety and righteousness.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– I don't know

Notes: Whether selfishness is the root of the wickedness is not clearly explained in the text.

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– Yes

Notes: As stated above, the punishment Yahweh exacts is on those in power, his (and his king's) enemies, and the wicked.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– I don't know

Notes: This depends on how one interprets being "brought down to Sheol." Psalm 49 gives a dreary picture of Sheol, for example, and the general attitude towards afterlife existence in the netherworld is hardly paradise (see Gilgamesh, Enkidu, and the Netherworld, e.g.).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Notes: The punishment involves a general execution of justice. But it is emphasized that Yahweh is in charge of all and deals out life and death to all and it occurs during this lifetime.

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– No

↳ Political failure?

– No

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Yes

Notes: If this is the meaning of "broken bows."

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– No

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Sickness or illness?

– No

Notes: If we can include hunger here.

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– Yes

Notes: If we can say that the one who bears many children will languish (v.5b).

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: Hunger

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Those subjected to barrenness, hunger, military domination will gain children, be satiated, and take on strength. The king will also be exalted.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

Notes: Injustice, at least in part.

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Notes: If only for the sake of piety/righteousness.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– I don't know

Notes: As with the issue of punishment, perhaps being "raised up" is a reference to afterlife, but this overdetermines the text, in my opinion.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

Notes: A theme of the poem emphasizes the reversal of the current state of affairs.

↳ Consists of good luck?

– No

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– Yes

Notes: The king is strengthened and the poor sit with princes.

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– Yes

Notes: Strongly implied in v.10.

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– No

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– No

Notes: Not mentioned.

↳ Other?

– Specify: Yahweh offers protection for his faithful.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: Later interpreters will see Hannah's allusion to the future king as a form of messianism. But in its historical context, this text is not messianic.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: There are no prescriptions for norms. The text may imply them, however.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– No

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– No

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - No
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - No
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - No
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - No
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - Yes
 - Notes: Insofar as v.10 explains that Yahweh will give strength to his king. It is not a general advocacy for strength, however.
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - No

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

Notes: See v.9, those who are faithful receive protection from the deity.

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– No

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– No

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: Unspecified in the text.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: In the ancient world, elite scribal groups. Then, religious groups (i.e., Judaism and Christianity).

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Not clear for antiquity. In later periods, specifically within Judaism biblical texts are ritually disposed of.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: Admittedly, it is unclear for 1 Sam 2:1-10. However, scribal groups most likely learned and trained with some of the texts in the Hebrew Bible, or similar texts (Schniedewind 2019)

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Notes: There are no formal regulations regarding education or scribal culture in the Hebrew Bible per se. Characters that write are male, and this is typical of ancient scribal practices (though some women do write as we know, e.g., Enheduanna). 1 Samuel 2:1-10 offers no such comments.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: 1 Samuel 2:1-10, Barkay, Gabriel, Marilyn J. Lundberg, Andrew G. Vaughn, and Bruce Zuckerman. "The Amulets from Ketef Hinnom: A New Edition and Evaluation" 334 (May 2004). <https://doi.org/10.2307/4150106>.

Reference: 1 Samuel 2:1-10, Schniedewind, William M.. The Finger of the Scribe: How Scribes Learned to Write the Bible. New York: Oxford University Press, 2019.

Reference: 1 Samuel 2:1-10, Suriano, Matthew. A History of Death in the Hebrew Bible. Oxford University Press, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780190844738.001.0001>.

Reference: 1 Samuel 2:1-10, Barton, John. A History of the Bible: The Book & Its Faiths. Penguin Books, 2019.

Reference: 1 Samuel 2:1-10, Stavrakopoulou, Francesca. God: An Anatomy. Knopf, 2022. https://books.google.com/books/about/God_an_Anatomy.html?hl=&id=v79WEAAAQBAJ.

Reference: 1 Samuel 2:1-10, Schmid, Konrad, and Jens Schroter. The Making of the Bible: From the First Fragments to Sacred Scripture. Cambridge: The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2021.

Reference: 1 Samuel 2:1-10, Rendsburg, Gary A.. How the Bible Is Written. Peabody: Hendrickson, 2019.

Reference: 1 Samuel 2:1-10, Singletary, Jennifer Elizabeth. "Incomparable or Prototypical: Yahweh Among the Gods in the Hebrew Bible". In With the Loyal You Show Yourself Loyal: Essays on Relationships in the Hebrew Bible in Honor of Saul M. Olyan. University Park: Pennsylvania State University Press, 2021.

Reference: 1 Samuel 2:1-10, Knowles, Michael P.. "'the Rock, His Work Is Perfect': Unusual Imagery for God

in Deuteronomy XXXII" 39, no. 3 (July 1989). <https://doi.org/10.2307/1519607>.

Reference: 1 Samuel 2:1-10, Gray, Taylor. "Anthroponymic Evidence for the Divine Epithet *ḫūr-". *Nouvelles Assyriologiques Brèves Et Utilitaires*, no. 1 (2023): 18-20.

Reference: 1 Samuel 2:1-10, Sommer, Benjamin D. . *The Bodies of God and the World of Ancient Israel*. New York: Cambridge University Press, 2009.

Reference: 1 Samuel 2:1-10, Smith, Mark S. . *The Origins of Biblical Monotheism: Israel's Polytheistic Background and the Ugaritic Texts*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2001.

Reference: 1 Samuel 2:1-10, Machinist, Peter. "How Gods Die, Biblically and Otherwise: A Problem of Cosmic Restructuring". In *Reconsidering the Concept of Revolutionary Monotheism*. Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 2011.

Reference: 1 Samuel 2:1-10, Parker, Simon B.. "The Beginning of the Reign of God: Psalm 82 as Myth and Liturgy". *Revue Biblique* 102 (1995): 532-59.

Reference: 1 Samuel 2:1-10, Edelman, Diana V. , ed.. *The Triumph of Elohim: From Yahwisms to Judaisms*. Edited by Diana V. Edelman. Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1996.

Reference: 1 Samuel 2:1-10, Ulrich, Eugene. "5.1 Textual History of Samuel", 2020.
http://dx.doi.org.ezaccess.libraries.psu.edu/10.1163/2452-4107_thb_COM_0005010000.

Reference: 1 Samuel 2:1-10, Brotzman, Ellis R., and Eric J. Tully. *Old Testament Textual Criticism: A Practical Introduction*. Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2016.

Reference: 1 Samuel 2:1-10, Gray, Taylor. "1 Samuel 2:1-10: Hannah's Prayer". In *Prayer in the Ancient World*. Leiden: Brill, n.d..